

YOUNG MEMBERS' TECHNICAL CONFERENCE 2024

IESL
YMS

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

29th SEPTEMBER 2024

Organized by The Young Members' Section
The Institution of Engineers, Sri Lanka

Medium Scale Industry – Store Grease Mixer

Piyarathna M.W.S.B and K.T.K.M. De Silva

Abstract: In industrial environments, efficient lubrication is crucial for ensuring machinery's smooth operation and longevity. Grease, a versatile lubricant, typically consists of base oil, thickener, and additives. However, a persistent issue is oil separation from stored grease, which diminishes its effectiveness and compromises machinery maintenance. This project is addressed by enhancing grease mixing equipment in lubrication rooms, aiming to reduce oil separation and maintain grease quality through advanced technology and improved mixing methods. The primary challenge is maintaining grease quality over time, as oil separation can lead to increased wear, overheating, and premature machinery failure. Ensuring consistent grease quality reduces maintenance costs and improves machinery reliability and operational efficiency. By developing an advanced grease mixing machine able to mitigate oil separation, preserve lubricant integrity, and extend equipment lifespan. Grease prevents friction, dissipates heat, and seals against contaminants and moisture, making its consistent quality crucial. This design focuses on improving the mixing process to prevent oil separation and ensure high grease quality, incorporating advanced mixing techniques and monitoring systems. By continuously mixing the grease, this machine prevents oil separation, reducing machinery damage risk. The design features innovative mixing mechanisms that handle high-viscosity fluids, applicable across industries like dairy and food processing. This optimization enhances lubrication practices, improving machinery performance and longevity. The final design's advanced mixing technology revolutionizes handling high-viscosity fluids, transforming lubrication practices in multiple fields and providing a robust solution to a critical industrial challenge.

Keywords: Oil separation, Base oil, Grease mixing

1. Introduction

Efficient lubrication is vital in industrial settings to guarantee the seamless functioning and durability of machinery. Grease, a multifunctional lubricant, often comprises of basic oil, thickener, and additives. However, a recurring problem is the separation of oil from stored grease, which reduces its efficiency and undermines machinery upkeep [1]. This project aims to improve grease mixing equipment in lubrication rooms to minimise oil separation and ensure high-quality grease by utilising advanced technology and enhanced mixing methods.

The greatest obstacle lies in preserving the quality of grease over time, as the separation of oil can result in heightened friction, excessive heat generation, and early malfunction of machinery [2]. According to Figure 1, despite the controlled temperature of the grease storage, several factors still contribute to grease bleeding. Ensuring consistent grease quality is crucial for minimising maintenance expenses and enhancing the dependability and operational efficiency of machines. By creating an improved grease mixing machine, able to prevent oil separation, conserve lubricant integrity, and increase equipment lifespan.

Grease prevents friction, distributes heat, and protects against impurities and moisture, making its consistent quality vital [3].

Figure 1 - An industrial real example of grease bleeding (oil separation) in storage.

Our focus is mainly on 180 kg grease barrels, which cannot be mixed by hand, resulting to wasted worker time and ergonomic difficulties. Additionally, manual mixing does not ensure grease quality [4]. Medium-sized factories, which use many machines and require considerable quantities of grease for maintenance, can considerably profit from this machine. The final design focuses on optimising the mixing process to prevent oil

separation and assure good grease quality, using modern mixing techniques and monitoring technologies.

Approximately grease density is 0.92 g/cm^3 and Base Oil Viscosity is around 100 to 150 centistokes at 40°C . By continuously mixing the grease, this machine minimises oil separation, decreasing machinery damage risk. The design contains novel mixing mechanisms that manage high viscosity fluids, suitable across industries including dairy and food processing. This optimization improves the lubrication techniques and improves the operation and life of the machinery [5]. The final design's enhanced mixing technology changes the approach to managing highly viscous fluids, altering lubrication methods in various industries while providing a durable solution for addressing a major industrial challenge.

2. Literature Review

The importance of grease mixing machines in industrial applications, particularly those designed to avoid oil separation, has been thoroughly explored [6]. The main difficulty addressed by these machines is the tendency of lubricating greases to segregate oil under both static and dynamic situations. This separation can affect the grease's capacity to lubricate efficiently, resulting to increased wear and potential machinery failure [7]. Oil separation is impacted by various factors, including the type of thickener used in the grease, the temperature, and the mechanical stresses produced during operation.

Figure 2 – Grease bleed testing apparatus kit.

Traditional methods for testing oil separation, such as DIN 51817, include long-term static tests that determine the mass fraction of separated oil [8]. However, newer techniques like analytical photo-centrifugation enable for real-time monitoring of oil separation at various temperatures and mechanical loads,

providing more specific insights into the grease's stability and performance characteristics [9]. According to several industrial standards, permissible oil separation levels might range: ASTM D6184 (Standard Test Method for Oil Separation from Lubricating Grease) normally regards less than 5% by weight after 30 hours at 100°C as acceptable [10]. DIN 51817 normally considers below 5% by weight after 168 hours at 40°C as acceptable. IP 121/ASTM D1742 frequently regards $< 3\%$ by weight as acceptable [11],[12].

Moreover, like Figure 2 recent improvements in grease formulation and testing have focused on enhancing the consistency and stability of greases under storage and operational settings. [13]. Studies have demonstrated that adjustments to the grease composition, such as the introduction of particular polymers or additives, can considerably boost the retention of oil inside the grease matrix, thereby retaining its lubricating qualities over extended periods. The development of new testing methods and improved formulas emphasises the continued efforts to maximise grease performance in many industrial applications [14].

These advancements are vital for sectors such as automotive, manufacturing, and food processing, where dependable lubrication is essential for preserving equipment performance and lifetime. This comprehensive analysis of current literature underlines the vital function of grease mixing machines in guaranteeing the quality and effectiveness of lubricating greases, hence minimising serious damage and promoting the longevity of industrial gear [15].

3. Material and method

3.1 Machine parts

The final design of the grease mixing machine combines numerous important components to enable successful and efficient mixing of high-viscosity greases. The principal mixing mechanism contains a blade type Anchor Impeller Mixer, which is designed for handling the thick viscosity of industrial greases [16]. Power transfer is enabled through a sturdy gearbox, ensuring reliable and consistent torque delivery to the mixing blade.

To further increase the mixing process as Table 1 has mentioned, the machine adds a fixed metal baffle, which disturbs the flow pattern

and promotes thorough blending of the grease components. The machine is powered by an electric motor, giving a reliable and regulated power supply.

Table 1 - Designed grease mixer's functionality.

Function	Concept
Blade type	Anchor impeller Mixer
Power transmission type	Gearbox
Mixing Enhancement Mechanism	Fixed metal baffle
Power Source	Electric Motor
Control Method	Timer-Based
Mixing Frequency	Daily Mixing
Container Type	Manufacturer grease barrel
Mixing Level Regulator	Spring loaded movable plate
Safety Features	Emergency Stop
Mixing Speed	Fixed Speed
Maintenance	Scheduled Maintenance

Additionally, the design features a spring-loaded movable plate, which functions as a proper mixing level regulator, ensuring that the grease is consistently mixed throughout the whole batch. These components jointly contribute to the machine's ability to maintain high grease quality, avoid oil separation, and improve overall lubrication performance in diverse industrial applications.

4. Machine design and construction

Figure 3 - 3D model of the grease mixing machine

The design and construction of the sophisticated grease mixing machine are illustrated in the accompanying Figure 3. The machine is based around a manufacturer grease barrel, ensuring interoperability with common grease storage containers. At the basis of the design is the electric motor, which drives the entire mixing procedure. Power transmission is governed by a sturdy gearbox, which distributes torque to the shaft, allowing the operation of the anchor blades [17]. These blades, built as an Anchor Impeller Mixer, are specifically tailored for handling high-viscosity greases, ensuring thorough and constant mixing.

To boost the mixing efficiency, the machine adds a fixed metal baffle. This component alters the flow pattern within the barrel, promoting more effective blending of the grease. Additionally, the machine incorporates a spring-loaded plate, which works as a proper mixing level regulator [18]. This spring mechanism ensures that the plate maintains the correct pressure on the grease, facilitating equal mixing throughout the barrel. The complete arrangement is enclosed with a metal lid, offering durability and protection during operation. Together, these components operate in harmony to avoid oil separation and maintain good grease quality, hence decreasing maintenance costs and prolonging the lifespan of industrial gear.

4.1 Calculations

Efficient mixing of grease, a non-Newtonian and shear-thinning fluid, needs careful consideration of several essential characteristics [19]. The generalized Reynolds number (Re_g) assists in defining the flow regime, while the apparent viscosity (η) and average shear rate ($\dot{\gamma}_{avg}$) are crucial for understanding the fluid's behaviour under shear. Additionally, the power consumption and power number (N_p) are vital for constructing energy-efficient mixing procedures. These calculations inform the selection of impeller design, rotational speed, and vessel size to ensure optimal performance of the grease mixing machine [20].

The generalized Reynolds number Re_g for non-Newtonian fluids is defined as,

$$Re_g = \frac{Nd^2\rho}{\eta} = \frac{N^{2-n}d^2\rho}{m\left(\frac{3n+1}{4n}\right)^n B^{n-1}} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

(fluid density (ρ), power law index (n), consistency index (m), impeller rotational speed

(N), impeller blade diameter (d), and stirred vessel diameter (D)

The apparent viscosity (η);

$$\eta = m(\dot{\gamma}_{avg})^{n-1} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

The average shear rate is,

$$\dot{\gamma}_{avg} = K_s N \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

where K_s is the shear rate constant, and N is the impeller rotational speed.

$$K_s = B\left(\frac{3n + 1}{4n}\right)^{\left[\frac{n}{n-1}\right]} \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

$$B = \left[9.5 + \frac{9\left(\frac{D}{d}\right)^2}{\left(\frac{D}{d}\right)^2 - 1}\right] \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

Then apparent viscosity (η) can be expressed as.

$$\eta = m\left(\frac{3n + 1}{4n}\right)^n B^{n-1} N^{n-1} \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

The power consumption is determined by integrating the local power transferred by the impeller to the fluid over the impeller surface. It may be stated that the power consumption, denoted as P, is solely determined by the impeller transferring energy to the fluid. Under these circumstances:

$$P = \eta \int_{vessel\ volume} Q_v \cdot dv \dots\dots\dots (7)$$

where dv is the viscous dissipation and P is power. The power number N_p is calculated as

$$N_p = \frac{P}{\rho N^3 d^5} \dots\dots\dots (8)$$

5. Results and Discussion

The finite element analysis (FEA) of the grease mixing machine's lid and spring-loaded metal plate demonstrated that the stress and displacement levels are within safe limits [21]. The highest von Mises stress is below the yield strength, indicating the components' robustness and reliability. Further analysis details are presented in later parts.

4.1 Metal Lid 3D Simulations

Illustrated in Figure 4, the simulation depicts the von Mises stress distribution in the lid of a grease mixing machine composed of AISI 316 stainless steel. With this degree of dimension, the research indicates that the stress levels stay below the yield strength of the material, assuring structural integrity while grease storage.

Figure 4 - FEA simulation result of the Von Mises Stress on the selected faces of the Machine Lid.

The research reveals that the greatest displacement is around 0.684 mm shown in Figure 5, which is within acceptable limits, suggesting that the material retains structural stability under the imposed stresses.

Figure 5 - FEA simulation result of the Displacement on the selected faces of the Machine Lid.

Figure 6 - FEA simulation result of the FOS on the selected faces of the Machine Lid.

According to Figure 6, the factor of safety (FOS) distribution for a grease mixing machine's lid built from AISI 316 stainless steel under static load conditions reveals a minimum FOS of 1.1, signifying general safety but with regions of higher stress that need attention. To improve the design, increasing the thickness in places with the lowest FOS will distribute stress more uniformly and enhance overall strength. Multiple finite element analysis (FEA) iterations with different design adjustments should be undertaken to discover the ideal mix of changes that optimize the FOS.

4.2 Spring loaded plate 3D Simulations

Figure 7 - FEA simulation result of the Von Mises Stress on the selected faces of the Spring-loaded plate.

The simulation of this section depicts the von Mises stress distribution shown in Figure 7, for the spring-loaded plate in a grease mixing machine, built from AISI 316 stainless steel. With this dimension the stress distribution indicates that the plate maintains within acceptable operating limits during grease storage, ensuring correct mixing without material failure.

Figure 8 - FEA simulation result of the Displacement on the selected faces of the Spring-loaded plate.

This static displacement distribution shown in Figure 8, for the spring-loaded plate in a grease mixing machine, constructed above material reveals that the plate deforms within

permissible limits under operating loads, assuring its functioning in appropriate grease mixing.

Going through Figure 9, not only the factor of safety (FOS) distribution of a spring-loaded plate utilized in a grease mixing machine, with a minimum FOS of 1.2. Then, the design is close to its failure point under the maximum projected load, which may not give enough durability or safety margin in practical applications [22]. It would be good to reassess the design, maybe reinforcing the structure or utilising a material with a higher strength to ensure a safer and more robust performance.

Figure 9 - FEA simulation result of the FOS selected faces of the Spring-loaded plate.

5. Conclusions

The grease mixing machine for medium-scale enterprises greatly optimises grease quality and machinery lubrication by minimising oil separation, decreasing wear, and increasing equipment lifespan. This machine currently remains in the design stage. In the future, it will have to be fabricated, and the results must be achieved to verify the reliability of the machine design. Its revolutionary design manages high-viscosity fluids, saving machinery downtime and maintenance expenses. This cost-effective technology enhances operating efficiency and dependability, giving major economic benefits. Not only for grease mixing, but this design is also excellent for mixing high-viscosity fluids on a cheap budget and can be enhanced according to special needs.

References

1. Triveni, B., Vishwanadham, B., Madhavi, T., & Venkateshwar, S., "Mixing Studies of Non-Newtonian Fluids in an Anchor Agitated Vessel", Chemical Engineering Research and Design, Vol. 88, No. 7, July 2010, pp. 809-818.
2. Baart, P., van der Vorst, B., Lugt, P. M., & van Ostayen, R. A., "Oil-bleeding model for

- lubricating grease based on viscous flow through a porous microstructure", *Tribology Transactions*, Vol. 53, No. 3, 2010, pp. 340-348.
3. Ellis, E. G., "GREASE BLEEDING, ITS MECHANISMS & MEASUREMENT", *Industrial Lubrication and Tribology*, Vol. 10, No. 9, September 1958, pp. 20-25.
 4. Camousseigt, L., Galfré, A., Couenne, F., Oumahi, C., Muller, S., & Tayakout-Fayolle, M. "Oil-bleeding dynamic model to predict permeability characteristics of lubricating grease", *Tribology International*, Vol. 183, 108418, 2023.
 5. Huang, L., Guo, D., & Shizhu, W., "Film Thickness Decay and Replenishment in Point Contact Lubricated with Different Greases: A Study into Oil Bleeding and the Evolution of Lubricant Reservoir", *Tribology International*, Vol. 93, 2016, pp. 620-627.
 6. Triveni, B., Vishwanadham, B., Madhavi, T., & Venkateshwar, S., "Mixing Studies of Non-Newtonian Fluids in an Anchor Agitated Vessel", *Chemical Engineering Research and Design*, Vol. 88, No. 7, 2010, pp. 809-818.
 7. Sosa, Y., "Review Lubricant and Grease Storage and Handling Practices: Following Safety Protocols and Procedures While Handling Lubricants is Extremely Important", *Plant Engineering*, Vol. 75, No. 5, May 2021, pp. 17-20.
 8. Cui, P., Hou, Z., He, L., Zheng, H., He, Y., Fan, Y., ... & Huang, Y., "Experimental Study on In Situ Storage of Grease-Lubricated Ball Screws", *Applied Sciences*, Vol. 14, No. 7, 2024, pp. 2734.
 9. Jacob, K. H., 'Oil Separation of Lubricating Greases under Static Conditions: Analytical Photo-Centrifuge and DIN 51817', *Lubricants*, Vol. 11, No. 3, March 2023, pp. 143.
 10. Westbroek, R., Habgood, B., & Williams, D., "Panta Rei: Everything Flows", In 24th International Colloquium Tribology, expert verlag GmbH, Vol. 24, January 2024, pp. 185.
 11. Razali, M. N., Aziz, M. A. A., Hamdan, W. N. A. W. M., Salehan, N. A. M., & Rosli, M. Y., "Synthesis of grease from waste oils and red gypsum", *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, Vol. 11, No. 113, 2017, pp. 154-159.
 12. Bergmann, E. A., "A Small Grease Kettle", *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry*, Vol. 39, No. 4, April 1947, pp. 498-500.
 13. Kay, J., Panesar, R., & Turner, D. A., "A Micrographic Comparison of Greases: STRATCO® Contactor™ Reactor vs. Kettles", *NLGI Spokesman*, Vol. 68, No. 9, 2004, pp. 20-32.
 14. Froishteter, G. B., & Denisenko, V. N., "Selection of Mixer for Reactors in Lubricating Grease Manufacture", *Chemistry and Technology of Fuels and Oils*, Vol. 25, No. 01, January 1989, pp. 31-36.
 15. Tanguy, P. A., Thibault, F., & De La Fuente, E. B., "A New Investigation of the Metzner-Otto Concept for Anchor Mixing Impellers," *The Canadian Journal of Chemical Engineering*, Vol. 74, No. 2, 1996, pp. 222-228.
 16. Ameer, H., & Ghenaïm, A., "Mixing of Complex Fluids in a Cylindrical Tank by a Modified Anchor Impeller", *ChemistrySelect*, Vol. 3, No. 26, 2018, pp. 7472-7477.
 17. Havener, D. M., "Design of a Spring Loaded, Tilting Binding Plate," 2009, pp. 9-52.
 18. Sorokin, S. V., "Analysis of Vibrations and Energy Flows in Sandwich Plates Bearing Concentrated Masses and Spring-like Inclusions in Heavy Fluid-Loading Conditions," *J. Sound and Vibration*, Vol. 253, No. 2, February 2002, pp. 485-505.
 19. Ameer, H., "Effect of some parameters on the performance of anchor impellers for stirring shear-thinning fluids in a cylindrical vessel," *Journal of Hydrodynamics*, Vol. 28, No. 4, 2016, pp. 669-675.
 20. Karray, S., Driss, Z., Kchaou, H., & Abid, M. S., "Hydromechanics Characterization of the Turbulent Flow Generated by Anchor Impellers," *Engineering Applications of Computational Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 5, No. 3, 2011, pp. 315-328.
 21. Akin, J. E., "Finite Element Analysis Concepts: via SolidWorks", World Scientific, 2010.
 22. Shih, R., "Introduction to Finite Element Analysis Using SolidWorks Simulation 2014", SDC Publications, 2014.